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SHEEHAN'S SYNDROME CLINICAL CASE

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Relevance. *Sheehan's syndrome (SS) is an ischemic necrosis of the pituitary gland due to severe postpartum hemorrhage, characterized by varying degrees of impaired pituitary hormone synthesis. As recently as 50 years ago, SS occurred in 10–20 cases per 100,000 women. It is believed that due to improved obstetric care, the prevalence of the disease has decreased, especially in developed countries. According to various estimates, the prevalence of SS in India is 2.7–3.9% among women over 20 years of age who have given birth. The prevalence of SS among the population of Iceland in 2009 was 5.1 per 100,000 women [1, 2]. It is known that during pregnancy, the pituitary gland increases in volume (up to 36%) due to hypertrophy of prolactin-secreting lactotrophs, which leads to vulnerability of the pituitary gland to ischemia - this explains the absence of SS in non-pregnant women [3]. The enlarged pituitary gland compresses the branches of the superior pituitary artery (SPA), which feed the adenohypophysis, but during the physiological course of pregnancy and childbirth this causes a minimal decrease in blood supply.*

Keywords: *Hypovolemia, hypotension, antipituitary, hypopituitarism.*

Introduction. In massive postpartum hemorrhage leading to hypotension and hypovolemic shock, blood flow to the gland is reduced, and compression of the branches of the pituitary artery prevents the restoration of adequate perfusion, causing ischemia of the adenohypophysis with subsequent necrosis [4]. In case of pituitary atrophy on ≤50% of the remaining tissue is sufficient for adequate functioning, and with a larger volume of damage, SS usually manifests itself [5]. It is assumed that tissue destruction continues after the initial necrosis. Necrotic tissues are antigens that

promote the production of antibodies to pituitary cells. Antibodies can also affect the remaining pituitary tissue: the percentage of intact tissue decreases, causing an even greater decrease in hormone production and disease progression [3]. However, it is known that antipituitary antibodies are not detected in all patients with SS, and not all pregnant women with severe postpartum hemorrhage are found to have SS; this suggests that the pathophysiology of the syndrome is still insufficiently studied [6]. SS was first described by H. L. Sheehan in 1937 [7]. Patients with a similar syndrome were previously reported by other pathologists: L. K. Glinsky in 1913 [8] and M. Simmonds in 1914 [9], but they believed that the underlying causes of pituitary necrosis observed at autopsy were thrombosis or bacterial embolism of the pituitary artery due to postpartum sepsis. Sheehan was more accurate in defining the etiopathogenesis and consequences of postpartum pituitary necrosis: massive postpartum hemorrhage causes spasm or thrombosis of the pituitary arteries, leading to hypopituitarism. Sheehan observed the manifestations of the disease based on morphological studies of the pituitary gland and other endocrine glands obtained during autopsy of women with SS. He demonstrated that the common histological aspect was necrotic areas in the pituitary gland due to decreased arterial blood flow. In approximately half of the cases, necrosis was observed to extend to the entire anterior pituitary gland, leading to total hypopituitarism; in the other half of the cases, necrosis was limited, leading to partial failure of the anterior pituitary gland [10]. Manifestations of SS, depending on the number of affected adenohypophysis cells and the level of hormones secreted by it, can vary from disruption of the synthesis of one hormone to complete cessation of the functioning of the anterior pituitary gland, leading to coma and even death [11]. Lack of lactation and resumption of the menstrual cycle after childbirth complicated by severe bleeding are the most important signs in the diagnosis of SS [12]. Other symptoms that may suggest SS in a patient with a typical obstetric history include complaints of weakness, decreased performance, and drowsiness, which may reflect the manifestation of electrolyte disturbances such as hyponatremia, hypothyroidism, or adrenal cortex insufficiency [13, 14].

Clinical case. Patient P., 34 years old, came for an appointment on 14.08.2023 complaining of severe weakness, decreased appetite, nausea, palpitations, and weight loss of 1.5 kg over the past week. The described complaints appeared at the end of May 2023 and gradually progressed. It is known from the anamnesis that on May 24, 2023, the patient had an urgent delivery (at 39 weeks); a boy was born (body weight - 3450 g, length - 51 cm), full-term (Apgar score - 8-9 points). Before the pregnancy, she considered herself healthy. First referred to an endocrinologist for interpretation of pregnancy tests on 10/12/2022 (gestational age 6 weeks): blood TSH - 5.6 mIU/L (norm 0.2-2.5), free T4 -12.1 pmol/L (norm 12-22). Diagnosis: "subclinical

hypothyroidism AIT?". Prescribed L-thyroxine (50 mcg/day), iodomarin (200 mcg/day). Blood TSH from 11/22/2023 (gestational age 12 weeks) - 1.8 mIU/L. She received the recommended therapy throughout the pregnancy and for 1 month after childbirth, then canceled it on her own. On 05/24/2023, an urgent spontaneous birth occurred. 40 minutes after delivery, hemodynamic disturbance with difficulty breathing and weakness were noted, massive bleeding with a significant decrease in hemoglobin to 59 g/l was diagnosed (before delivery, hemoglobin was 116 g/l). The patient was transferred to the intensive care unit of the regional hospital, where she urgently received a blood transfusion. She was discharged from the hospital in satisfactory condition on the 7th day, upon discharge, hemoglobin was 88 g/l. From June to August 2023, there were repeated visits to a therapist with complaints of progressive weakness, anorexia, weight loss, in addition, the patient did not lactate and the menstrual cycle did not recover. The therapist gave general recommendations on nutrition and taking multivitamins. In July-August 2023, the patient underwent self-examination: MRI of the brain and pituitary gland dated July 21, 2023 - the pituitary gland size is normal, has a homogeneous signal; August 11, 2023: blood TSH - 0.0025 mIU / l, free T4 - 28.67 pmol / l (norm 9-19.05), free T3 - 4.24 pmol / l (norm 4.0-7.4 pmol / l), hemoglobin - 118 g / l. She consulted an endocrinologist, a diagnosis of diffuse toxic goiter, thyrotoxicosis was made. Antibodies to the TSH receptor were not detected, there were no signs of infiltrative ophthalmopathy. The T4/T3 ratio was not calculated, although the most likely diagnosis for the patient shortly after childbirth is postpartum thyroiditis. Thyrozol was recommended (10 mg 3 times a day). However, the patient did not follow the recommendations and on August 14, 2023, she sought an appointment with an endocrinologist at the Ya. Turakulov Siberian Federal Scientific and Practical Center for Epidemiology and Epidemiology. Based on the results of an objective examination at the time of the visit: general condition is satisfactory, skin is pale, hair thinning in the groin and axillary areas, height is 161 cm, body weight is 52.8 kg, body mass index is 20.4 kg / m², pulse is 82 per minute, satisfactory properties, blood pressure on the left arm is 90/50 mm Hg. Heart sounds are clear, clean. Vesicular breathing, There are no wheezing sounds. The abdomen is soft and painless. The thyroid gland is not enlarged, vascular noise above the gland is not heard, nodular formations are not palpated. Eye symptoms are negative. Clinically, there was no impression in favor of thyrotoxicosis. Given the patient's complaints and the presence of severe hypotension, it was necessary to exclude adrenal cortex insufficiency. Additional examination is recommended: determination of cortisol, adrenocorticotrophic hormone (ACTH) in the blood, blood test for antibodies to thyroid peroxidase (TPO), antibodies to the thyroid-stimulating hormone receptor (TSH). According to the examination results of 08/16/2023: cortisol - 1.8 nmol/l (normal 171–536), ACTH -

5.1 pg/ml (normal 0–46), antibodies to the TSH receptor - 0.75 IU/l (normal 0–1.75), antibodies to TPO - 7.7 U/ml (normal 0–34). Diagnosis: “postpartum thyroiditis, euthyroidism? Secondary adrenal insufficiency. Sheehan’s syndrome.” Treatment since 08/16/2023: cortef (50 mg/day: 30 mg in the morning, 20 mg at 16:00). Additional examination is recommended: follicle-stimulating hormone (FSH), luteinizing hormone (LH), estradiol, prolactin, somatotrophic hormone (STH). On the 2nd day of taking glucocorticoids, the patient noted an improvement in her well-being: weakness decreased, appetite appeared. According to the results of the additional examination dated 08/28/2023: FSH - 0.85 mIU/L (norm 3.5-12.5), LH - 0.41 mIU/L (norm 1.69-15.0), estradiol - 12 pmol/L (norm 90-860), prolactin - 121 µg/L (norm 130-540), free T3 -3.3 pmol/L (norm 2.6-5.7), free T4 -8.25 pmol/L (norm 9-19), TSH - 0.07 mIU/L (norm 0.3-3.4). On examination on 08/29/2023: the condition is satisfactory, the skin is of normal color and moisture, height is 161 cm, body weight is 54.1 kg (increase by 1.3 kg), BMI is 20.9 kg / m², blood pressure is 110/80 mm Hg, pulse is 78 per minute, rhythmic. Heart sounds are clear, clean. Vesicular breathing, no wheezing. The abdomen is soft, painless. Diagnosis: anterior pituitary insufficiency. Sheehan’s syndrome. Secondary adrenal cortex insufficiency. Secondary hypothyroidism. Secondary hypogonadism. Therapy was adjusted: cortef - 10 mg / day (1 tablet in the morning and 1/2 tablet at 16.00); Euthyrox (L-thyroxine) - 25 mcg once a day, in the morning, on an empty stomach, 40 minutes before breakfast; femoston 2/10. During therapy, dynamic control of analyzes from 09/15/2023: cortisol in daily urine - 267.96 mcg / day (norm 58-403), free T3 - 3.3 pmol / l (norm 2.6-5.7), free T4 - 14.5 pmol / l (norm 9-19). Further monitoring by an endocrinologist and gynecologist is recommended. Thus, a typical variant of detection of autoimmune thyroiditis with subclinical hypothyroidism during pregnancy and the appointment of adequate replacement therapy is presented. After childbirth, complicated by massive bleeding, the district endocrinologist noted a decrease in the TSH level and an increase in the content of free T4 with a normal T3 level, which was interpreted as diffuse toxic goiter, thyrotoxicosis. Without clinical and laboratory data in favor of diffuse toxic goiter, the patient was prescribed antithyroid drugs. Progressive deterioration of health led the patient to another consultant, who was able to evaluate the clinical and anamnestic data and suspect SS. Urgent determination of the blood cortisol and ACTH levels allowed the prescription of adequate glucocorticoid therapy, to which, after additional examination, other replacement therapy was added.

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